

08 On Discrete Euclidean Space

Sydney Ernest Grimm*

15 January 2021

The paper is the eighth post of the blog “Discrete Euclidean Space” at <https://www.conceptualframeworks.org>. The post is about the gravitational field as a property of the flat Higgs field in vacuum space.

More fields

Gravity in its most simple appearance is the mechanism that is responsible for the fall of all objects in the direction of the surface of the Earth. Actually it is about the concentration of matter because a planet is just a very large object.

Nevertheless, there is something strange about gravitation because the field of gravitation is not in rest in relation to the moving objects. This in opposite to the universal electric field and the Higgs field. Figure 1 shows an electromagnetic wave. The electric (E) and magnetic (B) amplitudes exist everywhere in the universe and emerge from the basic properties of the units of discrete space (see **01**). It shows that the electric field – the deformable part of every unit of discrete space (see **06**) – is in rest, like all the scalars of the Higgs field are in rest. But all the observable phenomena move in relation to each other and in relation to discrete space, the “creator” of the observable phenomena (like the general concept of QFT).^[1]

figure 1

That is why the gravitational field around an object in vacuum space isn't a universal field like the Higgs field and the electric field. The gravitational field is the result of the creation of matter. Actually, it is a bit comparable with the negative electric charge around the electron.^[2]

If the gravitational field is the consequence of the creation of matter – rest mass – it is impossible to understand the gravitational field if we have no insight in the mechanism that is responsible for the creation of matter.

figure 2

The 2 images above – figure 2 – show in a schematic way the concentration of quanta within a region of discrete space. Every quantum has the constant linear speed of light therefore the concentration of the quanta is moving in relation to the structure of discrete space itself. In the right image the concentration has increased but the velocity of the concentration decreased because every unit of discrete space can transfer only 1 quantum during 1 t_c synchronous with all the other units of discrete space in the universe. It simply costs far more change ($t_c \times h$) to transfer a high amount of topological deformation to the adjacent units.

The difference between mass and matter is rest mass. The nuclei of atoms have rest mass and this local surplus of energy – the rest mass – is the result of the decrease of one or more local scalars of the Higgs field (see **07**). Above a certain amount of local concentrated quanta the scalar in the unit in the centre of the concentration has to decrease its magnitude (radius). It means that there is a transfer of a part of the volume of the scalar – “the outer shell” – to the deformable part of the unit, the electric field. The phenomenon is known as the Higgs mechanism^[3] and the consequence of the local decreased scalar is the emerging of new vectors within the scalars of *vacuum space* around. Because the local decreased scalar has ruined the symmetry (figure 3) of the scalar vectors in vacuum space around the decreased scalar.

figure 3

References:

1. Art Hobson (2013), “*There are no particles, there are only fields*”.
Am. J. Phys. 81 (3), March 2013, 211-223
DOI: 10.1119/1.4789885
arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1204/1204.4616.pdf
 2. Robert A. Millikan (1913). “*On the elementary electrical charge and the avogadro constant*”
https://history.aip.org/history/exhibits/gap/Millikan/01_Millikan.html
 3. Jeremy Bernstein (2011). “*A question of mass*” American Journal of Physics **79**, 25 (2011)
<https://doi.org/10.1119/1.3487939>
- * City of Amersfoort, the Netherlands
Email: segrimm@conceptualframeworks.org
Orcid: 0000-0002-2882-420X

Newtonian gravitation

If every scalar in vacuum space has the same magnitude and one scalar in the middle decreases its radius it is like there has been forced a hole in the structure. As a result the induced scalar vectors in vacuum space around will point in the direction of the decreased scalar. In other words, these new created scalar vectors are added to – or subtract from – the existing vectors of the magnetic field.

The number of the decreased scalars of an object has a direct relation with the mass of the object. Because the total mass of an object depends mainly on the number of protons and neutrons. Every proton and neutron has rest mass that originates from decreased scalars of the flat Higgs field. That is why in 1787 Isaac Newton^[4] described gravitation as a force with the help of a relation between the masses of the objects and the mutual distance between the involved objects:

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$$

[F is the gravitational force; m_1 and m_2 are the masses of the two objects; r is the distance between the centres of the masses; G is the gravitational constant]

The mechanism that determines the direction of the motion of matter doesn't differ fundamentally from the influence of the magnetic field on the direction of the quanta of the electric field. However, because vectorization of the scalars by the creation of matter is the result of the concentration of quanta – see figure 2 – the influence of gravity is only observable between concentrations of quanta – matter – at the macroscopic scale. The force of gravitation isn't detectable at the scale of a single nucleus.

Figure 4 shows – in a schematic way – the resulting vectors of the induced gravitational field, the simplified structure of discrete space (cubes) and the spherical decline away of the origin of the vectors (red circles).

figure 4

Figure 4 shows in a clear way that the force of gravitation is a push force from the vectorized flat Higgs field around the matter. A concept that is experimentally confirmed because the force of gravitation can be shielded with a sheet of light,^[5] A sheet of linear quanta – fixed amounts of topological deformation at right angles to the vectors – will affect the vectors of the field of gravitation. Vectors – see figure 5 – that determine the distribution of the transfer of quanta between the faces of the involved units.

figure 5

But the scalar vectors that are generated by the continuous transfer of quanta are not 100% identical to the scalar vectors of Newtonian gravity. The cross-section in figure 6 shows why.

figure 6

The amount of topological deformation in the joint face between unit A and B touches the scalar of unit B (red arrows). It can be thought as an addition to the scalar vector of A in line with the point of contact between the scalars of A and B. But if the scalar of unit B decreases the influence of the topological deformation of unit A on the scalar of unit B still remains. But the decrease of the magnitude of the scalar of unit B interrupts the point of contact between A and B. Now the vector symmetry (black arrows) of the inscribed sphere of unit A is broken because there are only 11 points of contact with identical scalars left. This forced asymmetry inside the scalar of unit A is the origin of Newtonian gravity.

Quantum time isn't relative – see **03** – and space itself can not be curved because nearly everywhere in the universe the Higgs field is flat (which is known for decades). So I have to conclude that Albert Einstein's theory of Special and General relativity doesn't describe phenomenological reality in a consistent way. Nevertheless observations and experiments prove the reliability of the theory. That's why I have to conclude that Einstein's theory of gravitation is about an unknown macroscopic effect of discrete space.

References:

4. Isaac Newton(1787), "*Philosophiæ Naturalis Principia Mathematica*".
Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy.
<https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/spacetime-theories/#2>
5. Louis Rancourt and Philip J. Tattersall (2015),
"*Further Experiments Demonstrating the Effect of Light on Gravitation*".
Applied Physics Research; Vol. 7, No. 4; 2015
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/apr.v7n4p4>